

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BINARY POLYESTER BLENDS

Aleksandra Nešić, Ksenija Ilić, Branka Pilić

Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

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alexm@uns.ac.rs

Abstract: Poly(lactide) is the most widely used polyester from the biobased and biodegradable group of polymers. It is available and the price is affordable for high-volume applications. The main disadvantage of PLA is brittleness, thus, PLA is a low-impact polymer. For certain applications that require tailored mechanical properties, it is necessary to blend PLA with other polymers or modify it by adding plasticizers. In this work, PLA was blended with poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) and poly(butylene adipate terephthalate) (PBAT), where PBS or PBAT were added in amounts of 10, 20 and 30%, and thin films were produced using flat die extrusion. Those ratios were chosen because of the transparency of the films obtained from blended materials, since PLA is the most transparent of all alternative materials, and the addition of PBS or PBAT significantly affects it. Examination of mechanical properties resulted in a very high deviation of values within one sample, which indicates the immiscibility of PLA with other polyesters. Due to this fact, there were two approaches as the solution to the problem: the addition of a plasticizer/modifier and two-step processing, which gave better compatibility results.